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Fatty Acid Composition of *Fleurya interrupta* and *Ajuga macrosperma*

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As a part of our programme to explore the herbal drugs, we reported¹ the presence of a good number of amino acids from two endemic herbs of Tripura, *Fleurya interrupta* Gaudich (*Urticaceae*) and *Ajuga macrosperma* Wall (*Labiatae*). Now we report the fatty acid composition of these plants.

The ground aerial parts (150 g) of the young plant of *F. interrupta* were extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) by percolation method and the crude petrol extract was column chromatographed through silica gel to get an oil (0.9 g). The oil was saponified and the fatty acid mixture (0.4 g) was recovered in the usual manner, esterified with diazomethane and the resulting Me-esters were purified by passing through a silica gel column and analysed by glc technique. The components were identified² by comparing their retention times with those of the authentic samples in both 10% DEGS and 10% PEGA columns. The relative percentage abundances of the component fatty acids as calculated from the recorded peak areas of their Me-esters were as follows: 14:0 (8.22), 14:1 (5.61), 14:2 (5.16), 16:0 (24.5), 16:1 (3.82), 18:0 (5.13), 18:1 (9.55), 18:2 (2.5), 20:0 (1.75), 22:5 (3.2) and others unidentified (30.56%). The presence of unsaturated fatty acids was also confirmed by catalytic hydrogenation of a part of Me-ester mixture with 10% Pd–C followed by glc analysis of the hydrogenated product.

The plant *A. macrosperma* (300 g) was worked up in a similar manner, and the component fatty acids along with their relative percentage abundance determined were as follows: 12:0 (0.29), 12:1 (0.38), 14:0 (0.98), 14:2 (6.12), 16:0 (7.34), 16:1 (13.71), 16:2 (11.42), 18:0 (11.97), 18:1 (7.48), 18:2 (6.75), 18:3 (5.39), 20:1 (7.83), 20:2 (9.83), 22:0 (0.97), 22:1 (0.91) and others unidentified (8.63%).

The presence of unsaturated fatty acids was also confirmed in a similar manner as before.

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Fatty Acid Composition of Minor Seed Oils

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In continuation¹ of our screening programme of the seed oils, a study of six seed oils belonging to *Acrocarpus fraxinifolius*, *Casuarina equisetifolia*, *Legerstroemia therolli*, *Prosopis juliflora*, *Boerhaavia defusa* and *Dyospyros cardifolia* are reported and fatty acid composition of these oil-seeds are determined by glc.

The ground seeds were extracted with light petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) in a Soxhlet to afford the oil. Analytical values of seed oils were determined according to the procedures recommended by the AOCS² (Table 1). All the oils and their esters showed no conjugation or *trans*-unsaturation or any other functional groups in uv and ir studies. The quantitative examination of methyl esters was undertaken by glc. Identification of each acid was made by comparing its retention time with those of the standard samples of fatty acid methyl esters (Sigma and groundnut oil methyl esters).

The seed oil of *A. fraxinifolius* contains high percentage of oleic acid (76.3%). *C. equisetifolia* contains an unusual amount (78.5%) of essential fatty acid, i.e. linoleic acid. The seed oil compositional data indicate that the oils of *L. therolli* and *P. juliflora* contain palmitic acid in amount of 23.5 and 27.1%, respectively.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL VALUES AND COMPOSITION OF SEED OILS

Sl. no.	Oil	Iodine %	Sap. value	Fatty acid composition (%)								
				16:0	16:1	18:0	18:1	18:2	18:3	20:0	Others	
1.	<i>A. fraxinifolius</i> , Wight and Arn. (Caesalpinaceae)	8	70	192	18.8	—	3.4	76.3	1.5	—	—	—
2.	<i>C. equisetifolia</i> , Linn. (Casuarinaceae)	10	145	191	9.61	—	3.6	8.32	78.5	—	—	—
3.	<i>L. theroili</i> , Linn. (Lythraceae)	8	120	194	23.5	—	2.9	30.5	22.2	20.8	—	—
4.	<i>P. juliflora</i> , D.C. (Mimosaceae)	10	98	195	27.1	—	3.0	35.2	27.7	7	—	—
5.	<i>B. defusa</i> , Linn. (Nyctaginaceae)	10	50	195	98.8	1.36	2.76	52.0	2.76	—	—	22:0, 1.81
6.	<i>D. cordifolia</i> , Roxb. (Ebenaceae)	3	49	210	40.25	—	5.71	13.15	14.85	3.66	4.23	10:0, 2.82, 12:0, 13.82, 14:0, 1.76

Experimental

Infrared spectra (film) were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and ultraviolet spectra (methanol) with a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer. Glc analyses were carried out with a Perkin-Elmer 154 instrument equipped with DEGS column. Tlc studies were done on silica gel plates. A 20% aqueous solution of perchloric acid was used as the spraying agent.

Seeds were cleaned and analysed as reported³. Methanolysis of the oil with H₂SO₄ as catalyst yielded methyl esters of the fatty acids, which were analysed by glc. In general, the esters were examined by various tlc techniques prior to glc analysis to ascertain the presence or absence of unusual acids.

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Simultaneous Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(v) in Geological Materials with 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-pyrazolone

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THE present communication describes the extractive spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(v) present in geochemical samples using the reagent 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-pyrazolone (PMBP).

Experimental

The reagent PMBP was prepared by the literature procedure¹. Solutions of the required concentrations were prepared in chloroform-butanol (4:1) mixture. A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of vanadium was prepared from ammonium metavanadate in 1 M H₂SO₄ and diluted to 100 and 10 µg ml⁻¹.

A Varian 634 double beam spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements.

Procedure: Standard vanadium(v) solution (100 µg ml⁻¹) was shaken with 5 ml of 0.1M PMBP solution (5 ml) at pH 3 in a separating funnel for 5 min. The absorbance of the extracted complex against the reagent blank was measured at 490 nm. The effect of diverse ions was studied by adding their standard solutions into vanadium standard and extracting the mixture at pH 3 with PMBP solution. Analysis of vanadium in some real samples are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that 5 ml of 0.1M PMBP solution in chloroform-butanol (4:1) is sufficient to extract 100 µg vanadium(v) in the pH range 2.5–4.5,